

Copper(II) and Dioxouranium(II) Complexes with Biologically Important Ligands. Part-II : Cu(II) and UO₂(II) Complexes with Schiff Bases Derived from Coumarin Derivatives

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Copper(II) and UO₂(II) complexes with some bidentate Schiff bases derived from bergapten and some substituted anilines have been prepared. The structures of the complexes have been investigated by elemental analysis, uv and ir spectra and molar conductance. It is concluded that the anions of the Schiff bases are bonded to the metal ion as bidentate ligand and the chelated compound is not formed when the substituted aniline moiety is high electron withdrawing.

BERGAPTEN (I) and visnagin (II), which can be extracted together with medically important xanthotoxin and khellin from the Egyptian plants *Ammi majus* (L) and *Ammi visnaga* (L), respectively, are now used as starting materials in the synthesis of some coumarins with functional group and some flavones of the baicalein group¹.

(I)

(II)

In continuation of our work on metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from biologically important ligands, we report here the results of our studies on the complexes of Schiff bases derived from coumarin derivatives and some aromatic amines with Cu(II) and UO₂(II). Tentative structures have been proposed for the complexes on the basis of analytical, spectral and conductance data. The Schiff bases used in the present study are (IV a-e) as shown below.

(IV)

- a; R = C₆H₅-OCH₃-p (L₁).
- b; R = C₆H₄-OH₂-p (L₂).
- c; R = C₆H₅ (L₃).
- d; R = C₆H₄-OH-o (L₄).
- e; R = C₆H₄-NO₂-p (L₅).

Experimental

Preparation of the Schiff bases :

The furan ring of bergapten² was oxidised with chromic acid to yield 6-formyl-7-hydroxy-5-methoxy

(III)

coumarin (III). The desired Schiff bases (IV a-e) were obtained when III was condensed with the appropriate substituted anilines in 1 : 1 ratio in acetic acid. The structure of these compounds were confirmed by elemental analyses and ir spectral data.

Preparation of the metal Schiff base complexes :

The complexes were synthesised by adding equimolecular amounts of the Schiff bases to ethanolic solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O or UO₂(NO₃)₂·6H₂O. The reaction mixture was refluxed for ~ 3 hr. The solid complexes which precipitated were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel. They were analysed for carbon and metal content. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Several attempts were made to isolate the copper complex of L₄ and copper or dioxouranium complexes of L₅ in ethanol or dioxane medium but all failed.

Physical measurements :

The electronic spectra were measured with Pye Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 559 Infrared spectrophotometer using KBr disc. Conductance measurements were made with a Pye conductivity bridge. All the experiments were carried out at 25 ± 1°.

Results and Discussion

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the Schiff bases are characterized by three absorption bands in the

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE DATA FOR THE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Formula	Analysis% ; Found/(Calcd.)		Molar conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Decomp. temp. °C
	Carbon	Metal		
L ₁	64.36 (64.48)	—	—	170
[CuL ₁]Cl	49.24 (49.88)	14.08 (14.66)	64	212
[UO ₂ L ₁]NO ₃	31.75 (32.38)	39.92 (40.48)	64	> 300
L ₂	69.72 (69.90)	—	—	200
[CuL ₂]Cl	52.66 (53.07)	15.72 (15.60)	65	> 300
[UO ₂ L ₂]NO ₃	34.02 (33.75)	41.83 (42.18)	64	> 300
L ₃	69.01 (69.15)	—	—	182
[CuL ₃]Cl	52.23 (51.91)	15.82 (16.16)	65	> 300
[UO ₂ L ₃]NO ₃	32.18 (32.59)	43.70 (43.13)	74	> 300
L ₄	62.12 (62.00)	—	—	196
[UO ₂ L ₄]NO ₃	30.48 (30.91)	40.34 (40.91)	64	> 300
L ₅	59.15 (59.30)	—	—	> 300

the possible formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in all the cases (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Molar ratio method for Cu(II) complexes. (a) with L₁, (b) with L₂, (c) with L₃, (d) with L₄.

280-380 nm region. The band at 352-380 nm is assigned to an intramolecular charge transfer within the solute molecule. The band at 304-340 nm is attributed to the excitation of one of the lone pair of electrons on the oxygen atom to the lowest antibonding orbital (n-π*) of the carbonyl group⁵. The band at 280-288 nm is due to π-π* within the C=N bond influenced by charge transfer interaction⁶.

The spectra of these Schiff bases are different from those of their solutions with the Cu(II) ion in 1 : 1 molar ratio (5 × 10⁻⁴ M). This can be considered as an evidence of instantaneous complex formation between L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄ with Cu(II) in solution. The longer wavelength bands of the free ligands exhibit large red shift on complexation (390-400 nm). The lower energy of the intramolecular charge transfer (CT) in the complexed ligands is due to the presence of the high positive charge on the central metal ion which facilitates this transition.

The non-complexation with L₅ may be attributed to the presence of the strong electron attracting nitro group which reduces the basicity of the azomethine nitrogen.

Stoichiometry of the complexes :

The stoichiometry of the Cu(II) complexes formed with the Schiff bases L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄ was ascertained by using the molar ratio and continuous variation methods^{5,6}. The results revealed

Fig. 2. Continuous variation method for Cu(II) complexes. (a) with L₁, (b) with L₂, (c) with L₃, (d) with L₄.

Apparent formation constant :

The apparent formation constant (K_f) of the 1 : 2 complexes formed in solution was determined from the results of the spectrophotometric measurements of the continuous variation method⁷. The results (Table 2) reveal that the stability of the

TABLE 2—THE APPARENT FORMATION CONSTANT OF Cu(II) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Schiff base	K_f
L_1	7.60×10^9
L_2	4.35×10^9
L_3	2.71×10^9
L_4	3.13×10^9

Cu(II) complex depends largely on the molecular structure of the ligand and is in the order $L_1 > L_2 > L_3 > L_4$. This is in agreement with the complex forming tendency of these ligands where the basicity of the azomethine nitrogen decreases with the decrease in the electron donor character of the substituent. The low complex forming tendency of L_4 may be attributed to steric factors. Thus, the stability period of Cu(II) complex of L_4 is relatively short.

Infrared spectra :

The tentative assignment of some of the important bands of the Schiff bases and their metal complexes are recorded in Table 3. It is evident that significant

TABLE 3—SIGNIFICANT INFRARED BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF THE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR COMPLEXES WITH Cu(II) AND $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$

Formula	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$
L_1	2900	1630	1270
$[\text{Cu}L_1]\text{Cl}$	—	1625	1280
$[\text{UO}_2L_1]\text{NO}_3$	—	1620	1272
L_2	2900	1630	1278
$[\text{Cu}L_2]\text{Cl}$	—	1625	1285
$[\text{UO}_2L_2]\text{NO}_3$	—	1620	1285
L_3	2900	1625	1280
$[\text{Cu}L_3]\text{Cl}$	—	1620	1290
$[\text{UO}_2L_3]\text{NO}_3$	—	1620	1288
L_4	2900	1625	1280
$[\text{UO}_2L_4]\text{NO}_3$	—	1620	1290
L_5	2900	1625	1288

changes in the ir spectra of the ligands are observed on complexation.

In the case of free Schiff bases, no band appears beyond 2900 cm^{-1} . On account of intramolecular hydrogen bonding ($\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{N}$), the frequency of the hydrogen bonded OH is lowered to a considerable extent and overlaps with νCH vibrations exhibiting a broad band at 2900 cm^{-1} . This band is absent in the ir spectra of the complexes.

The strong band in the $1630-1625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in the ir spectra of the Schiff bases may be assigned to azomethine ($>\text{C}=\text{N}-$) grouping. The band is shifted to lower frequencies in the spectra of the complexes. This suggests that coordination of the Schiff bases with the metal takes place through the azomethine nitrogen⁹.

The band at $1270-1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the ligands is ascribed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic⁹. This band is found in the $1275-1290 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region in the spectra of the complexes, suggesting that the OH of coumarin moiety takes part in complex formation. The shift to higher frequency of the phenolic C-O in going from a hydrogen bonded structure to a covalent metal bonded structure may be due to the expected high mesomeric interaction in the complex, which is probably activated by the presence of the metal ion. This fact is substantiated by the elemental analyses and molar conductance of the solid complexes.

Molar conductance :

The molar conductance values of $10^{-3} M$ DMF solutions of 1 : 1 complexes have been found in the range $64-74 \text{ ohm}^{-2} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$ range. These complexes can therefore be regarded as 1 : 1 electrolytes¹⁰.

Accordingly, the structure of the complexes under study can be represented as follows.

In conclusion, the anions of the Schiff bases derived from coumarin derivatives under investigation are bonded to the metal ions studied as bidentate ligands. The two bonding sites are covalent bond through oxygen of the deprotonated hydroxyl group of the coumarin moiety and coordinated bond through azomethine nitrogen. This tends to the stable six membered chelating ring. The presence of strong electron withdrawing group in the aniline moiety decreases the stability of the complexes.

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